

**JOURNAL OF ETHICS
AND DIVERSITY IN
INTERNATIONAL
COMMUNICATION**

OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL

WWW.OPENACCESSJOURNALS.ED

15	History of Socio-Economic Development of the Village of Uzbekistan	Ch.Kh. Temirova	58-61
16	Zoning Politics and Consequences in Uzbekistan	Normatov Otabek Maxamatjonovich,	62-66
17	Echographic Prediction of Fetal Growth Retardation Syndrome in Complicated Pregnancy During a Pandemic	Ikhtiyarova Gulchekhra Akmalovna, Ikhtiyarova Gulchekhra Akmalovna, Xudoykhulova Feruza Samadovna	67-70
18	Ecological-Faunistic Analysis of the Helminthofauna Redentia In Jizzakh Region	M. A. Mamatqobilova, O. N. Avalbaev, G. B. Matmuratova	71-74
19	Economic Security” and its Theoretical Fundamentals	Egamnazarov Shoxriyor Fayzi o’g’li, Axtamov Oxunjon Akmal o’g’li	75-82
20	Competence and Competency Approach in Vocational Education	Khairulla Gulomkadirovich Khojiev	83-84
21	Comparative Characteristics of Russian and Foreign Literature	Tursoatov Adham Asadovich, Mirzakulov Uktamjon Almardanovich, Ravshanova Mahliyo Umidqizi, Choriev Quvonchbek Chorshanbievich	85-87
22	Instrumental Approach for a More Effective Management of Project Stakeholders	Potoko Silas Moraba	88-98
23	"Female Images in Modern Russian and Uzbek Prose"	Kalonova Nargiza Nurjovovna, Samanova Nasiba Batir qizi, Usmonaliyev Xurshid Husniddinovich, Haqnazarov Himoyiddin Mannonovich	99-100
24	Methodological Fundamentals of Ensuring Sustainable Innovative Development in the Region	Doston Xamidov	101-103
25	The History of Sambo	Begimkulov Oltiboy Juraevich	104-105

**Methodological Fundamentals of Ensuring Sustainable Innovative Development
in the Region***Doston Khamidov**Student of the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture*

Annotation: This article discusses sustainable innovation development strategies and methods, and you can learn about the role of industrial companies in this development process.

Keywords: Innovative, foreign, local, industry, method, economy, development, risk, result, action, region

An analysis of domestic and foreign literature has shown that the level and dynamics of development of the innovation industry is a key factor in economic growth for most countries. Consequently, the country's place in the world arena today is determined not by the abundance of labor and natural resources, but by the quality of human capital, the level of education, the practical application of knowledge and innovative activities. In the modern economic dictionary, "innovations are innovations in the field of technology and labor organization and management based on the use of scientific advances and best practices, as well as the use of these innovations in various fields.

The issues of managing the innovative development of the economy are complex and controversial because they depend on the interaction of several parties: the state, venture capital firms, scientists and inventors, and universities. In order to prioritize the economy as the main driving force of modern society, it is necessary to create an integral, complete and at the same time mobile and evolving strategic system and mechanisms for the commercialization of new technologies for the innovative development of the country.

Sectors capable of producing the latest technologies will be the electronics and nuclear industries, the information and communication industry, the aircraft and rocket and space industries, mobile communications, medicine and the chemical-metallurgical complex. Despite the gradual increase in the cost of mastering the latest technologies in the domestic economy, the share of the sixth tier remains insignificant in the modern economy. According to some forecasts, a qualitative jump will occur in 2015-2020.

Innovative development reflects a series of periods of various innovations, a set of innovations created and implemented, the accumulation of intellectual capital, the involvement of scientists in this activity, the human factor and activity, innovative organizations that are impossible without investment capital. The effectiveness of innovation is closely linked to the development of innovation and the life cycle of innovation, in which the stages of innovation emergence, early innovative development, late innovative development, maturity and crisis management, the decline of innovation and the new wave associated with the appearance. History shows that the introduction of new industrial technologies has always had a positive impact on economic growth and living standards of the population, which created the conditions for the development and implementation of other innovations at a new stage of development.

The role of industrial companies in innovation development is also significant, with sectoral associations playing a special role in the implementation, adoption and dissemination of industrial innovations, which are more widespread in Japan under the auspices of the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Industry. Russia's sectoral associations are also involved in science-intensive industries, such as machine-building, machine-building, and so on. played a major role in its development. If the so-called national associations of industrial companies (for example, in the United States) define the national vision of scientific and technological development of the country, in many regions the main task of industry associations is to increase the efficiency of enterprises based on the introduction of scientific and technical innovations. is a compromise. Some of the associations are

| e-ISSN: 2792-4017 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Volume: 1 Issue: 6

actively involved in the standardization and certification processes. Provides training and retraining of staff in new areas of scientific and technological development. One of the main goals of business associations is to help modernize production. Excessive concentration of production and the prevention of modernization of "poorly structured" industries is the work of a number of associations in Japan.

Management of innovative activity Innovative activity The activity of the department is primarily aimed at integration into national and international innovation systems, the formation of systems for their participants, including expertise, staff support and related project management. Coordinates the creation of innovative enterprises in this area and the activities of HSE scientific and educational departments in this area.

Management of innovative activity Innovative activity The activity of the department is primarily aimed at integration into national and international innovation systems, the formation of systems for their participants, including expertise, staff support and related project management. Coordinates the creation of innovative enterprises in this area and the activities of HSE scientific and educational departments in this area.

The implementation of innovations is associated with costs, so these costs should be taken into account when calculating efficiency. In analyzing the effectiveness of services, it is necessary to address the problem of evaluating performance. The results of using innovation directly depend on the results and costs taken into account. It is necessary to calculate the economic, scientific, technical, financial, resource, social, as well as economic effects.

Types and selection of innovation strategy: The firm's innovation strategy in the market is offensive and defensive in nature. The company has its own set of innovative strategies, usually defined by a coordinated market side. Such a set includes both dangerous (offensive) and safe (defensive) strategies. Attack strategy means striving and being a leading enterprise in terms of a defined segment of the market and innovation in sales. The adoption of an offensive strategy by the company to actively seek and develop innovations, both as a mastered and new areas of economic activity, requires major changes in the organizational structure.

However, as the practice of firms in industrialized countries suggests, usually even large and powerful enterprises are not able to use an aggressive strategy in a wide range of goods and do not take risks. As a rule, it applies only to one or more separate types of goods, provided that there are favorable conditions for its sale.

An analysis of the long-standing planning practice in the enterprises of our country shows that it is not focused on the development of the enterprise plan, but on the implementation of the established planning task. This is explained by the objective reasons why industrial enterprises used to operate in the past, as well as the tasks facing enterprises in the early stages of economic development. Apparently, this practice does not correspond to the current conditions of management. A complex situation inherent in the enterprise economy today is related to the administrative command system of management that used to exist. It envisages centralized planning and distribution of resources without taking into account the real needs of production, free financing of production investments from the state budget, individual control of producers, the absence of state-owned ownership and some forms of management. There were also the following: institutional disruption and separation of participants in the production process due to the lack of a multi-stage structure of management and the dependence of income and investment on the final results of operations.

The above-mentioned reasons, as well as a number of reasons related to the disruption of economic relations, have led to imbalances in various sectors of processing and the economy, deepening deficits and declining production discipline have led to economic decline in the country and led to a recession in the innovation sector, which exacerbated the situation in the consumer market and money circulation. These problems and complexities increase the need for real planning, which allows to form an adequate strategy, the development of the enterprise.

Strategic innovation planning is a common system of enterprise planning in a market economy. The object of strategic innovation planning in the enterprise will be innovative activity, which, considering it, can be said as follows. In the current situation, the strategy of innovation activity in the enterprise takes into account the objective needs of innovation strategies based on the main goals and objectives of enterprise development, resource provision and risk factors, the state of the external environment and individual innovation opportunities.

| e-ISSN: 2792-4017 | www.openaccessjournals.eu | Volume: 1 Issue: 6

In order to increase the potential revenue of a new competitive product its creation and production at the level of modern techniques and technologies. Development and implementation of scientific and technical policy in the field of innovation became the main content of his activities. The strategic importance of ITTKI in the implementation of innovation strategies will increase, and at the same time the level of risk in their implementation increases. innovative activity from all other types of activities in the enterprise and from everyone first, it is done in conjunction with production and marketing.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. <https://fayllar.org/reja-innovatsiya-samaradorligi-tushunchasi.html>
2. file:///C:/Users/user/AppData/Local/Temp/innovatsion_menejment-1.pdf
3. <https://forumshoes.ru/uz/innovacionnaya-deyatelnost-i-ee-vidy-innovacionnaya-deyatelnost/>
4. <http://staff.tiame.uz/storage/users/41/books/PCutQ9xsdLdumcyCfH26jsJwul4I2kVzoJ2EBzmC.pdf>
5. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2017/11/30/innovatsiya>